

GPU Simulations of Violent Flows with Smooth Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) Method

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Abstract

Graphics processing unit (GPU) accelerated supercomputers have proved to be very powerful and energy effective for to accelerate the compute intensive applications and become the new standard for high performance computing (HPC) and a critical ingredient in the pursuit of exascale computing. In this study, a quantitative comparison of a recent numerical treatment on GPUs which are applied on the solution of a violent free-surface flow problem by Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method will be presented. The performance and the scalability of the cards will be evaluated on sway sloshing problem in a tank by solving Euler's equation of motion and utilizing weakly compressible SPH method (WCSPH). The algorithms demands extensive computational power for the simulations require large number of particles as in a sloshing tank which is a two or three-dimensional complex geometry. Thus, the parallelization of the solver is the key for to utilize the method on a real industrial flow problem. The recent researches showed that WCSPH approach is highly suitable for adopting it into GPU cards because of its explicit approach. The comparisons will show that how many times the computational speed of the proposed method on the GPU is faster than that implemented on the CPU. For the sway-sloshing problem, the time histories of free surface elevations on the left side wall of the tank will be compared with experimental and numerical results available in the literature to show the accuracy of the method briefly and finally analyze the solver's efficiency on GPUs.

1. Introduction

The goals of this task have been to apply GPU implementation of an engineering simulation tool to a real and for PRACE application. The application is a Fortran based in-house Computational Fluid Dynamics code which is developed by the authors. The code uses Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method to calculate velocity and pressure distribution in the domain without using any computational grid. Due to its Lagrangian and meshless nature, the SPH method is an exceptionally suitable tool for modelling highly nonlinear violent flows with a free surface. The SPH method was introduced simultaneously by Gingold and Monaghan [1] and Lucy [2] to simulate compressible flow problems in astro-physics and later extended by Monaghan [3] to model incompressible free surface flows through using a Weakly Compressible SPH approach (WCSPH) which assumes that a fluid is incompressible if its density variation is less than 1%. In the SPH method, the continuum is represented by particle which carry fluid properties such as density, velocity and pressure, among others. These particles represent infinitesimally small fluid elements having finite volumes, and can interact with each other in each time-step through a weight function having a compact support domain. The relevant governing equations and boundary conditions are discretized in space over these particles.

Present work uses numerical remedies namely, density correction, VFS (Velocity-variance based Free Surface), and Artificial Particle Displacement (APD) algorithms [4] which helps to improve the accuracy and stability of the numerical scheme. Density correction algorithm should be included into the solution scheme because in

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WCSPH approach the pressure values are calculated through an equation of state which couples density and pressure values. The coupling of pressure and density brings the necessity of precise calculation of density values which has a significant importance while finding the pressure values of particles. In addition to density correction algorithm, VFS algorithm is applied only to free-surface particles while APD is used to regularize the arrangement of particles with fully populated influence domain, which are identified via the kernel truncation. A two dimensional sway- sloshing problem, which is well-accepted as a benchmark test case among SPH researchers, is solved using Euler's equation of motion. Sloshing problem is an important phenomenon in several engineering fields including marine, oil-gas and aeronautics because of its significant effects on design of gas, fuel and water tanks and transporting them with ships and aircrafts. The results from this work maybe interesting for CoEs and research communities such as SPHERIC, SPPhysics, CNRS, CNR-INSEAN and MARSTRUCT Network of Excellence.

The flow is modelled to test if the numerical treatment gives accurate and reliable results in the numerical simulations. The code developed to perform simulation is written in Fortran 90. The results from some of serial simulations performed in CPU are priminelary published in Ozbulut et al. [5]. Due to explicit approach of the method, it is highly suitable for parallelization by using graphic cards. In this work, first results from GPU performance test is presented.

2. Numerical modelling

SPH is a Lagrangian method where the flow domain is represented by a finite number of movable particles which can carry the characteristic properties of the problem at hand such as mass, position, velocity, momentum, and energy. The core of its mathematical formulation is based on the interpolation process, wherefore the fluid system is modeled through the interaction among particles, which is achieved by an analytical function widely referred to as the kernel/weighting function $\mathbf{W}(\mathbf{r}_{ij}, \mathbf{h})$ where \mathbf{r}_{ij} is the magnitude of the distance vector,

$$\bar{\mathbf{r}}_{ij} = \bar{\mathbf{r}}_i - \bar{\mathbf{r}}_j \quad (1)$$

for a pair of particles, namely, the particle of interest \mathbf{i} and its neighboring particles \mathbf{j} , and h is the smoothing length. Here, $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_i$ and $\bar{\mathbf{r}}_j$ are the position vectors for the particle \mathbf{i} and \mathbf{j} , respectively, and as to be understood, boldface indices \mathbf{i} and \mathbf{j} are particle identifiers to denote particles. An arbitrary continuous function (which can be scalar, vectorial, or tensorial), $A(\bar{\mathbf{r}}_i)$, or concisely denoted as \mathbf{A}_i , can be interpolated as

$$A_i \cong \langle A(\bar{\mathbf{r}}_i) \rangle \equiv \int_{\Omega} A(\bar{\mathbf{r}}_j) W(r_{ij}, h) d^3 \bar{\mathbf{r}}_j \quad (2)$$

where the angle bracket " $\langle \rangle$ " denotes the kernel approximation, $d^3 \bar{\mathbf{r}}_j$ is the infinitesimal volume element inside the domain, and Ω represents the total bounded volume of the domain. The function \mathbf{A}_i may represent any hydrodynamic properties such as velocity, pressure, density, and viscosity. The kernel function used in the current work is a quintic spline with the form of

$$W(R, h) = \alpha_d \begin{cases} (3 - R)^5 - 6(2 - R)^5 + 15(1 - R)^5, & 0 \leq R < 1 \\ (3 - R)^5 - 6(2 - R)^5, & 1 \leq R < 2 \\ (3 - R)^5, & 2 \leq R < 3 \\ 0, & R \geq 3 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{r}_{ij}/\mathbf{h}$ and α_d is a coefficient that depends on the dimension of the problem such that $120/h$, $7/(478\pi h^2)$ and $3/(359\pi h^3)$ for one, two and three dimensions, respectively [6]. Upon using the SPH approximations which involve the replacement of the integral operation over the volume of the bounded domain by the mathematical summation operation over all neighboring particles \mathbf{j} of the particle of interest \mathbf{i} , and the differential volume element by the $\mathbf{m}_j = \rho_j$, and performing some tedious mathematical manipulations.

3. CUDA implementation

SPH method requires calculation of the weight functions between the particles in neighborhood as described in Equation 2 and 3. In order to calculate the function, the distance between every particle combination should be calculated (Equation 1) and compared with a certain radius (smoothing length) shown in Fig 1. Calculating the neighbourhood of each particles is computationally demanding. TAU profiling tool [7] has also been used and it showed that neighbourhood finding and weight function calculation of the particles are computationally heavy spots in entire process (approx. 70% of the calculation time).

Fortran DO loops were modified with CUDA Fortran functions in a simple way and calculations in the loops were sent to the CUDA cores of the graphic card to be processed in different threads. The particle distance calculation routine (Equation 1) with CUDA Fortran implementation is shown in Fig. 2. This routine calculates the distance between particles at each time step according to distance vector (Equation 1) definition as mentioned in Numerical modelling section. The source code is compiled by PGI's CUDA Fortran [8] compiler *pgfortran* version 16. CUDA Fortran is a Fortran analog to NVIDIA CUDA C, CUDA Fortran includes a Fortran 2003 compiler and tool chain for programming NVIDIA GPUs using Fortran. CUDA Fortran is supported on Linux, macOS and Windows.

Figure 1: Neighbourhood for particles (smoothing length) left, simulation domain for sway sloshing tank, right

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DO i=1,ntotal
  j=threadIdx%x + blockDim%x * (blockIdx%x - 1)
  if (j <= ntotal) THEN
    dx(i,j)=x(i)-x(j)
    dy(i,j)=y(i)-y(j)
    ra(i,j)=SQRT(dx(i,j)*dx(i,j)+dy(i,j)*dy(i,j))
  END IF
END DO

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Figure 2: Generated CUDA kernel

4. Results

For the development, a single NVIDIA's GeForce GTX 690 card combining two Kepler GPUs (4 GB memory in total) is used. Simulations performed with NVIDIA's Tesla K20 (Kepler architecture) with 6 GB memory. GPU version of the particle distance subroutine (Fig.2) performed 15 times faster over serial CPU version which is run on a Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-3820 CPU with approx. 3000 particles. However this doesn't bring a significant speed up for code in overall. In the same way, CUDA implementing of weight function (Equation 3) makes the subroutine running 6 times faster compare to CPU version running serial however this doesn't bring too much benefit for the entire simulation time. The overall speed-is x2.2

Figure 3: Comparison of digital time series of the water level evolution close to the left wall where $\zeta(t)$ denotes the water level change in time [5].

Figure 3 present the results of the current work as compared to experimental and numerical results in terms of digital time series of free surface elevations for two different positions of the tank, (namely, close to the left wall and at the mid section of the tank). It can be seen from Fig. 3 that the periods and the amplitudes of the harmonic motion of the fluid are in very good agreement with the numerical results and experimental data of the literature. The aim of comparative results given in Figure 3 is to show the compatibility of our simulation results with the given experimental and numerical based literature data. Along this line, it is not easy to claim an idea as "one numerical result is more accurate than the other". But one can see that the periods and the amplitudes of the harmonic motion of the fluid are in very good agreement with the numerical results and experimental data of the literature.

Figure 4: Particle positions and pressure distributions at given instants (time is advancing from a to h) [5]

As a final output of this study, the free surface profiles and the pressure distributions at given instants are shown in Fig. 4. From the figures it can be seen that the particles starts to move when the harmonic motion of the tanks starts, and splash to upper and side walls of the tank in time (time advances from a to h). The color shows the pressure levels. It can be seen that the free surface is captured well and the splashing of water to the tank ceiling is simulated with the particles fairly. It is from the figures that the VFS+APD treatment provides satisfactory particle distribution and free surface profiles wherein particle clustering and particle splashing or separation from the free surface are eliminated.

5. Conclusions and Future work

Porting of some of the essential subroutines of the Fortran code to the GPU platform by using CUDA did not bring a substantial speed up for entire simulation however it showed the potential of high performance computing ability of the graphics cards for SPH method specifically. Parallelization of weight function subroutine has some difficulties because of mathematical relations of particle neighborhood and of unbalanced load distribution on the threads. This will be overcome by using dynamic parallelization. It is expected that this will bring substantial performance acceleration.

Simulations have been performed with low resolution (fewer particles) and with higher resolution better speed up is expected by overcoming the memory bottleneck in GPU cards. To perform simulations with higher particle numbers, in the future, MPI libraries will be used for taking advantage of the enhanced computing power of several GPUs working simultaneously. These let the code performs for flows around more complex geometries, in fact 3D problems. More test runs with different number of particles will be performed and how scalability/performance of presented solution scales with problem size and number of GPU threads/blocks will be observed. Using GPUs or multicore platforms is regarded as important and necessary steps for enabling a software for an exascale future. However current algorithms should be restructured and adopted to the new platform.

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